

XAI meets Data-Centric AI: The Need to Explain Data Processing

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Data preprocessing is an essential part of any AI system, as indicated by the current trend of data-centric AI. However, until now, explainability efforts have almost exclusively focused on models. Choices in preprocessing, such as handling missing data, outliers, scaling, and class balancing, and their effects are currently not part of the explanations. If we continue this way, we are left with only a partial understanding of the model's outputs. This transparency deficit creates risks for accountability, fairness, model performance, and more. We argue why we need full pipeline transparency and, as part of that, data preprocessing explainability, even in an age of AutoML and foundational models.

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1 Introduction

The model-centric perspective of XAI research. The importance and popularity of explainable AI (XAI) research has increased with the popularity and omnipresence of AI. It addresses critical issues such as transparency for building trust, improving systems, and fulfilling regulatory requirements. However, most, if not almost all, research in the discipline is focused on the comparatively narrow goal of increasing a user's understanding of a trained model.

The case for full pipeline transparency. While researchers have rightly identified the importance of opaque model architectures, the steps leading up to model training, such as data collection, cleaning, engineering, and transformation, are largely disregarded in XAI research and related fields. However, these steps significantly impact the resulting outputs and, therefore, the fairness, trustworthiness, and overall effectiveness of AI systems. The motivational goal of explainability research is to make AI systems more transparent, and these processing steps before model training are an essential part of those systems. An explanation of only the model itself is an incomplete explanation; a genuinely holistic and human-centered approach to XAI must include full-pipeline transparency. This holds particularly true as more and more non-data scientists gain access to AI through libraries, non-code platforms, AutoML systems, and LLMs. The increased access has many benefits, but it also holds risks as users with less educational and foundational knowledge of data science are building systems. The emerging trend toward data-centric AI, which is a reaction to the significance of data quality and engineering in AI systems, also emphasizes this argument.

We, therefore, argue that one necessary next step in XAI research encompasses explaining the effects of preprocessing on model outputs. To design effective, sustainable, and responsible data preprocessing systems, data scientists need to know (1) how large the impact on the resulting model is, (2) what steps might cause adverse effects for individual model outputs, (3) how the model behavior, in addition to model outputs changes, is affected, (4) how preprocessing steps influence each other, and (5) how the selection of an implementation for a step affects the system.

2 The Open Problem in Explainability Research

XAI research has become a large and active field. However, so far, its scope is limited.

XAI Research isolates model explanations. Even extensive surveys with different goals such as taxonomy, meta-analysis, open challenges, comparison, evaluation) almost exclusively cover model explanations. For example, the recent survey by Abusitta et al. [1] covers various approaches to model explainability, but contains neither existing work nor open

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problems regarding other stages of AI. Saranya and Subhashini [12] do an extensive literature review and address future work across many sectors. They identify a deficit in the quality of the data used in research but do not mention explainability work beyond models. Schwalbe and Finzel [14] provide one approach among many to create a taxonomy, a meta-review, and a method review. They state that "the goal of the process is to achieve making an AI system's actions and decisions transparent as well as comprehensibly", but continue to treat the model as the only part of the system, not the many steps leading up to and following the creation of that model. A meta-survey by Saeed and Omlin [9] from 2023 analyzed 73 survey papers from the area of XAI, classifying them into three phases of the AI life cycle: Design, Development, and Deployment. Only three of the covered surveys belong to the design phase, two covering the quality of the data used and one the number of samples a user can inspect and the selection of these samples/explanations. This distribution reveals a research gap between the procurement and selection of data and the model training process.

Bridging the gap between training dataset explanations and model explainability. Training dataset explanations [2] have been a previous step in pursuing full pipeline transparency. They inspect the original training dataset and allow users to judge its properties and the effect on the model outcome. Following that in the data life cycle, the training data is further processed before model training. Depending on the data and model, the extent varies, and with that the effect.

Previous Work. XAI literature reveals little existing research around transparency in data preprocessing.

Dasu and Loh [4] propose evaluating the effect of data cleaning by measuring changes in the statistical properties of the data itself. Statistical distortion reflects how much the process skews the data relative to the achieved glitch improvement. While this can be a helpful perspective on data, it neglects the relationship with the rest of the AI system, hindering full pipeline transparency. The data affects model training, of course, and therefore, statistical distortion affects the model. However, different properties of data and, through them, preprocessing steps interact very differently with different model architectures. Data scaling, for example, is pointless for some architectures but essential to others. In pursuing full pipeline transparency, it is necessary to always look at data, preprocessing, model, and training together.

Gonzalez Zelaya [5] approaches this holistic view by measuring changes in model output. They introduce volatility, which covers the likelihood of a data point receiving a different model output and a learned model to approximate it efficiently. While this approach considers the interplay between preprocessing and model, the change in model output is a very limited source of information. The change for a data sample right along the decision surface and at a maximal distance would weigh the same. Changes in model behavior that do not result in a change of output, i.e., the same result for a different reason, are not considered at all. From the perspective of XAI, however, that is a particularly interesting case as it is similar to a common motivational challenge in the field: Models achieving high accuracy through undesired features or patterns. Additionally, the community has long concluded that no singular approach to model explainability will appropriately cover every circumstance, intent, and user [8]. Why should that be different when explaining other steps of the pipeline?

3 The Path Forward

The movement toward data-centric AI and why it matters. As in XAI, the research on AI has been very focused on models, model architectures, training, and hyper-parameters for a long time, while data and its handling were undervalued [11]. This focus, in conjunction with fixed and limited datasets, hindered the ability of models to transfer from research into practical application, generalize from one problem to another, or achieve the highest possible accuracy

[16]. Data-centric AI focuses on increasing both the quality and quantity of data to make contained information accessible to the model in training. It is also important to avoid unfair, discriminatory, or otherwise harmful systems. Combining model-centric AI and data-centric AI yields optimal results, and they should be combined and developed in conjunction with one another. This development of AI research outlines how XAI, too, could (and should) evolve in the next few years.

The context of process-centric explanations. Yurrita et al. [15] have made the case for process-centric explanations. This perspective tries to overcome the focus of XAI on outcome explanations and include choices made in the process in the explanations. They also make an argument for full pipeline explainability because considering the entire lifecycle is necessary to provide contestability in decision-making processes. We can take inspiration from their design when designing data preprocessing explanations as part of full pipeline transparency. As they derive the explanations from what might be contested, we should derive the content of preprocessing explanations from the information needed for the application scenario. One such application would be the design phase of an AI system, where explanations should reflect the impact of each preprocessing step in a way that describes its usefulness to the system. Yurrita et al. [15] argue that information should cater to decision subjects. Similarly, preprocessing explanations need to take a form that is useful to the target audience, which will be different in different use cases. Lastly, they suggest holistic evaluation protocols. This is also important for preprocessing explanations, which should be measured and evaluated by the process outcome in the context of the full pipeline.

One explanation approach does not fit all. These examples show that one way of explaining preprocessing will not work for all circumstances. This mirrors model-centric XAI research, where it is already established that a broad spectrum of approaches is not simply the symptom of the search for an optimal system but rather a necessity [8]. This line of thought can also be expanded to strengthen our argument for preprocessing explainability in the first place: If different forms of representations, ways of procuring explanations, and metrics for evaluation are needed, depending on the circumstances of the application, why should the model be the only aspect worth looking at for all of them?

Human-centered perspective and context. When developing and applying data preprocessing explanations, we must build on all the existing work and discussion from the XAI and related communities. This means:

- Not regarding each system in isolation, but considering the interaction between data, data preprocessing, model, and application.
- Allowing for human interaction or human-in-the-loop systems for trust and better performance.
- Considering the still present trade-off between accuracy and transparency [1].
- Learning from related research even if it pursues a different goal, such as fairness measures for preprocessing [3].
- Considering transparency in the context of responsible AI, fairness/bias mitigation, accountability, regulatory changes, and more.
- Participating in a discussion on which areas AI should be applied to and where inherently interpretable systems or post-hoc explanation systems are societally responsible.
- Empowering those involved in creating, deploying, and monitoring AI systems instead of reducing flexibility through automation.
- Building inclusive and culturally sensitive AI systems with all voices heard.

Beginning of a topology for preprocessing explanations. In the same way that the model-centric XAI community is structured along a number of dimensions[6], preprocessing explanations can also be designed along several characteristics. According to the use case they solve, they can be classified according to:

- *Design*: intrinsic vs. post-hoc
- *Model Dependence*: model-specific vs. model-agnostic
- *Scope*: local vs. global explanations
- *Data-type*: tabular/relational, text, images, stream data, ...
- *Target Audience*: data scientists, end users, domain experts ...

However, there are still several properties that are generally desirable for all approaches although they might not always be equally achievable. These desired qualities which construct a basis for evaluation can in part be adapted from XAI research. They include correctness, complexity, robustness and more. Nauta et al. [7] provide an overview over these characteristics, their applicability to different approaches, different names used for similar concepts and how to evaluate them.

For preprocessing explanations we suggest a few additional criteria:

- *Model-insight*: How is the model considered in the explanation process? Not at all, model output changes, model internals...
- *Granularity*: What degree of detail is considered in the preprocessing? The whole process, individual steps...
- *Diversity*: What kind of preprocessing can be explained? What are restrictions on input pipelines or steps?
- *Exploration vs. Investigation*: How freely is the user able to investigate? Are individual steps or problems targeted? Or are insights general independent of user preconceptions?
- *Interaction*: Are steps explained in isolation? Is there interaction with other preprocessing steps covered? If so, independent of position in the pipeline?

4 Interaction with Current Trends

Recent trends in AI research have given some users the impression that the challenge of data preprocessing is being solved through end-to-end systems. Large language models (LLMs) seem to suggest that instead of curating data, users can simply feed anything they have to the model in training. If these systems are on the rise, do we still need preprocessing pipelines at all. AutoML systems handle model selection, parametrization, and training for the user to build the optimal system. Since good preprocessing is dependent on the model, how should users still build their own?

So given these trends, do we still need data preprocessing and with it preprocessing explainability?

Democratization of AI through AutoML and LLMs. Recent developments in AI, such as AutoML and generative AI/foundational models/LLMs, have led to huge progress in democratizing access to AI technology and allow users with little to no data science background to use and build models. This positive development contributes to reducing inequalities and allowing more domain expertise to enter the field. Based on these trends, it can seem easy to argue that it becomes less important to pay attention to the individual steps of the process as long as the result is satisfactory, making full pipeline transparency redundant. However, quite the opposite is true for several reasons. As the accessibility of AI increases, the amount of solid foundational skills of the average user decreases. Additionally, the more the field as a whole grows, the harder it becomes to know about all relevant background aspects. That makes it more important to help users understand what is interacting in the full pipeline, not less.

AutoML is a heterogeneous landscape without design for complete understanding. With current AutoML systems, the situation for data preprocessing is quite heterogeneous. Many, especially early, systems do not include any data preprocessing steps, leaving this task up to the user, who might not fully understand the need, process, or implication of the process. It also means once again that data preprocessing happens completely separate from model selection and training, which unintentionally biases the resulting model choice and might limit the best possible result. Other systems do cover data preprocessing to a varying extent. Salhi et al. [10] identify 11 current AutoML platforms that include a subset of data cleaning, integration, reduction, and transformation. None of them have an intended way for the user to understand the data preprocessing that has happened. The commercial platforms usually expose very little of the inner workings to the outside. Due to the nature of AutoML, access to the resulting model is always necessary in some form and while this model may not be interpretable by design or presentation, post-hoc explainability methods exist that can provide insight. With regard to preprocessing, however, there is no implicit need to expose anything to the user, leaving it unclear what the system has or could have done, let alone how. Open source systems, by design, allow the user to modify the code to obtain more information on the process. However, the necessary changes vary widely in complexity and, in any case, require coding skills and a deeper understanding than these systems claim to necessitate. Only one in 11 systems provides the structure to access the resulting preprocessing pipeline. Even starting from that, there is a long way still to fully enabling, instructing, and guiding users to understand this part of the system fully.

LLMs are not on their own the solution to all problems. The most prevalent trend in any subfield of AI currently is the use of foundational models to tackle existing and new problems. While a lot of valuable research and applications have come from these advancements, they also expose several issues. They are neither intrinsically transparent and explainable, nor do we currently have suitable post-hoc methods, beyond asking an LLM to explain itself or another LLM, which is not more reliable than the original output. Even worse, they can contribute to what Sarkar [13] has called the "Illusion of Explanation", leading the user to believe they understand the process when they do not. In terms of accessibility, the natural language interface of LLMs is great for end users, but that is worth nothing if the information content of an explanation is not reliable. We cannot foresee what developments will happen over the next few years and what issues will be resolved. However, we cannot ignore that this technology neglects users who lack the resources or infrastructure to leverage large datasets and complex models, increasing inequalities. This issue is critical for lower and middle-income countries and other areas disadvantaged by structural inequalities. At the same time, these groups face challenges that make data preprocessing more important in traditional systems, such as data quality issues caused by social inequalities, propaganda, and lack of resources available for data collection, as well as transparent system design. Resources needed for effective foundational models also increase the difference between large commercial enterprises and research institutions, non-profits, and open initiatives. Data origin and usage are also usually a topic for discussion, both regarding quality and moral issues for LLMs and similar systems. These are all arguments to still prioritize data quality compared to quantity and not completely neglecting more traditional approaches in the hopes of foundational models solving issues in the future. Data preprocessing is an important part of data quality, and explainability, especially in a human-centered way, is a necessity of the process.

5 Conclusion

Data preprocessing is an essential part of any AI system, as indicated by the current trend of data-centric AI. However, until now, explainability efforts have almost exclusively focused on models. Choices in preprocessing, such as handling missing data, outliers, scaling, and class balancing, and their effects are currently not part of the explanations. If we

continue this way, we are left with only a partial understanding of the model’s outputs. This transparency deficit creates risks for accountability, fairness, model performance, and more. We need full pipeline transparency and, as part of that, data preprocessing explainability, even in an age of AutoML and foundational models. The human-centered perspective is as necessary in explaining preprocessing, as it is essential to model-centric XAI. Just like model-centric and data-centric AI complement each other, XAI will yield the best results, when explanations for data, preprocessing, models and more, are used together.

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